

LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL PROPERTIES OF LATIN SUFFIXES IN MEDICAL
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Abstract: The article discusses the lexical and grammatical features of derivational suffixes in the Latin language that create different meanings, illustrated through examples. Terms containing such suffixes constitute a relatively small part of medical terminology. These suffixes are attached to the root of a word and express various meanings. In Latin, there are noun-forming and adjective-forming suffixes. Knowledge of these derivational and semantic suffixes is important for the easy formation and translation of medical terms.

Keywords: suffixes, noun-forming suffixes, adjective-forming suffixes

As in many languages of the world, suffixes are widely used in Latin for the formation of medical, anatomical, and clinical terms. Suffixes are affixes that cannot function independently but are attached to a stem (root) to express various meanings related to lexical and grammatical features. Thus, the derived stem obtained in this way is called a suffixal stem. Suffixes perform an important classificatory function. In suffixation, different parts of speech — nouns, adjectives, and verbs — may serve as derivational stems. Certain suffixes combine only with the stems of specific parts of speech. For example, the suffixes *-al* and *-ar* combine with nominal stems, whereas *-io* and *-or* are attached to verbal stems.

The addition of a suffix beginning with a consonant to a word stem occurs through the use of a connecting vowel known as an interfex. In Latin words, the vowel *-i-* is commonly used, while *-o-* appears in words borrowed from Greek. For example: *cruc-i-formis* — cruciform; *tuberos-i-tas* — tuberosity; Greek *bronch-o-genus* — bronchogenic, etc.

In adjective formation, the suffix is attached to the stem of a noun in the genitive singular form. For example: *larynx, ngis* — *laryng-e-us*; *margo, inis* — *margin-al-is*; *cartilago, inis* — *cartilagin-e-us*; *occiput, itis* — *occipit-al-is*, etc.

By means of derivational elements, terms with broad semantic meanings are formed. Below are suffixes that, when attached to a stem, create new meanings.

I. Nouns Formed with Diminutive Suffixes

1. **-ul.** Examples: *lobus* — *lobulus* (lobe — small lobe); *vena* — *venula* (vein — venule); *lingua* — *lingula* (tongue — small tongue); *frenum* — *frenulum* (frenum — small frenum); *caput* — *capitulum* (head — small head); *tuba* — *tubulus* (tube — tubule); *nodus* — *nodulus* (node — nodule); *globus* — *globulus* (sphere — globule); *membrana* — *membranula* (membrane — thin membrane); *glomus* — *glomerulum* (ball — small ball); *vesica* — *vesicula* (bladder — vesicle); *ductus* — *ductulus* (duct — small duct); *fossa* — *fossula* (pit—small pit). There are 13 such nouns.

2. **-cul.** Examples: *canalis* — *canaliculus* (canal — small canal); *os* — *ossiculum* (bone — ossicle); *auris* — *auricula* (ear — auricle); *cutis* — *cuticula* (skin — cuticle); *tuber* — *tuberculum* (protuberance — tubercle); *venter* — *ventriculus* (abdomen — ventricle); *genu* — *geniculum* (knee — small knee); *radix* — *radicula* (root — rootlet); *corpus* — *corpusculum* (body — corpuscle); *dens* — *denticulus* (tooth — small tooth); *vas* — *vasculum* (vessel — small vessel). There are 11 such nouns.

3. **-ol.** Examples: *area* — *areola* (area — small area); *bronchus* — *bronchiolus* (bronchus — bronchiole); *arteria* — *arteriola* (artery — arteriole); *fovea* — *foveola* (pit—small pit). There are 4 such nouns.

4. **-ell.** Examples: *cerebrum* – *cerebellum* (brain — cerebellum); *lamina* – *lamella* (plate — small plate). There are 2 such nouns.

5. **-ill.** Example: *mamma* – *mammilla* (mammary gland — nipple).

II. Verb-to-Noun Suffixes Expressing Action or Process

1. **-io** (*-tio, -sio, -xio*). Example: *flexio* — bending. In Latin, such nouns denote operations, examination methods, treatment procedures, and physiological functions. Examples include: *operatio* — surgical operation; *palpatio* — palpation; *emotio* — emotion; *curatio* — treatment; *lectio* — lecture; *auscultatio* — auscultation; *percussio* — percussion, etc.

2. **-or** (*-tor, -sor, -xor*). Examples: *constrictor* — constrictor; *depressor* — depressor; *excavator* — excavator; *extensor* — extensor muscle; *tensor* — tensor muscle; *curator* — caretaker; *repetitor* — repeater or tutor.

Such nouns denote objects, instruments, devices, or persons engaged in various activities.

III. Verb-to-Noun Suffixes Expressing the Result of an Action

1. **-ura** (*-tura, -sura, -xura*). Examples: *curvatura* — curvature; *fractura* — fracture; *sutura* — suture; *fissura* — fissure; *commissura* — commissure; *junctura* — junction; *incisura* — incision or notch.

IV. Noun-to-Adjective Suffixes

1. **-osus**. Examples: *squamosus* — scaly; *fibrosus* — fibrous; *infectiosus* — infectious; *cavernosus* — cavernous, etc.

V. Adjective-Forming Suffixes Expressing Relation, Belonging, or Shape

1. **-al** (**is, e**) *vertebralis* — vertebral.

2. **-ar** (**is, e**). *maxillaris* — maxillary. Such adjectives are common in anatomical terminology and belong to the second declension adjective group.

3. **-ic** (**us, a, um**) (Greek origin) *thoracicus* — thoracic; *zygomatikus* — zygomatic; *gastricus* — gastric.

4. **-in** (**us, a, um**). *palatinus* — palatine; *uterinus* — uterine.

5. **-e** (**us, a, um**) (Greek origin). *oesophageus* — esophageal; *osseus* — osseous; *peroneus* — peroneal; *laryngeus* — laryngeal.

VI. Noun-to-Adjective Suffixes Expressing Similarity

1. **-ide** (**us, a, um**) (Greek origin)

rhomboides — rhomboid; *deltoides* — deltoid; *xiphoides* — xiphoid; *thyroides* — thyroid; *styloides* — styloid.

2. **-form** (**is, e**) *cruciformis* — cruciform; *pisiformis* — pisiform; *piriformis* — pear-shaped.

3. **-at** (**us, a, um**). *arcuatus* — arcuate; *lunatus* — lunate.

VII. Noun-to-Adjective Suffix Expressing “Carrying”

1. **-fer** (**a, um**). *seminifer* — seed-bearing; *sudorifer* — sweat-producing.

VIII. Noun-to-Adjective Suffix Expressing “Producing” or “Originating”

1. **-gen**. *carcinogenus* — carcinogenic; *pyogenus* — pyogenic, pus-producing.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Latin suffixes enrich the vocabulary of the Latin language by attaching to word stems and creating new meanings. This feature enhances the expressiveness and attractiveness of the language. Knowledge of Latin suffixes greatly facilitates the understanding, formation, and translation of medical terminology.

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